

The Opportunity Export of Coconut Shell Charcoal Briquettes from Indonesia in the International Market

Karin Sonaya Maudina ¹, Sahri Sahri ^{2*}, Tajidan Tajidan ³, Addinul Yakin⁴

¹ Undergraduate Student Agribusiness Study Program, Faculty Agriculture, University of Mataram

² Lecturer of Economics and Development Study Program – FEB University of Mataram

^{3,4} Lecturer of Agribusiness Study Program, Faculty Agriculture, University of Mataram

*Corresponding Author Name: Sahri Sahri

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7364938>

Published Date: 26-November-2022

Abstract: The purpose of this study is to know the opportunity to export briquettes charcoal shell coconut from Indonesia in the international market. Remember briquettes charcoal shell coconut is one-product plantations that have scored high exports. Briquettes charcoal shell coconut alone is product powder charcoal shell molded coconut with various forms like cubes, cylinders and faces six. Common models produced are briquettes shaped cube. As for the obstacles in export briquettes charcoal shell coconut this is lack of ingredient raw making briquettes charcoal shell coconut and way still making traditional because minimal knowledge as well as form unfinished marketing so large because lack of knowledge about international market access whereas Request to briquettes charcoal shell coconut this very high and steadily increase from abroad. Data used in study is obtained from books, journals, and websites that support hypotheses. In study this writer uses liberalism from Adam Smith, level nation-state analysis as well as study this use theory interdependence. Results of study show that briquettes charcoal shell coconut have great opportunity for marketing in the international market.

Keywords: Business International, Briquette Charcoal shell Coconut, Export, International Market.

I. INTRODUCTION

Trading International is something from transactions Among two countries or more to fulfill needs of each country (Apridar, 2018). Trading International plays an important role in developing the economy of any country, including Indonesia. In trading internationally every country involved inside it has a destination to get profit (Waugh, 2010). In an open system economy, every country tends to do export rather than import because activity export could interest domestic and foreign capital flows used in creating field jobs. Export is an activity for increasing the income of the government and in the end pushes growth in gross domestic product (Indonesia Investment, 2011).

International trade has an important role both directly and indirectly in the process of economic development. With the aim of increasing the country's foreign exchange earnings, creating jobs, and so on. The increasing volume of international trade will have an impact on changes in several variables in the economic sector so as to encourage economic growth (Marius, and Camelia, 2015).

Indonesia is a country that continues to strive to create field work and grow the economy in the process of developing its economy (Magdalena and Suhatman, 2020). Mature this development the economy in Indonesia is getting developed fast, see from the amount more exports increase every year. In 2012 Indonesia's export volume amounted to 600,136,600 tons with a value of US\$ 190,020,3 million. Then in 2021 Indonesia's export volume will amount to 621,667,800 tons with a value of US\$ 231,609.50 million. Thus, in the last ten years there has been an average increase in export volume of 1.09% per year. Meanwhile, the export value increased by an average of 3.31% per year in the last ten years. When viewed from

the export component, most of Indonesia's export volume comes from non-oil exports. In 2012, the contribution of non-oil and gas exports to the total export volume was 91.93% and oil and gas by 8.07%. The contribution of non-oil and gas exports to the total export volume continues to increase, so that in 2021 it will be 95.67% and oil and gas by 4.33% (BPS, 2022). Enhancement score export this tagged that connection trading international with other countries is better than other countries and things this will impact change score indicator economic a country.

The first commodity plantation Indonesia has potency donating foreign exchange to the country is coconut (Ahuja, et al 2014). Besides being beneficial for consumption daily, coconut also has potency to export to countries in need. Coconut also known as commodity commercial because every part from coconut could be utilized for various needs every day (Laura, 2016). One of the parts from coconut can make opportunity effort and potential for entering the export market is shell processed coconut becoming briquettes coconut. Briquettes coconut is a product made from powder charcoal made from shell coconut and printed in various shapes. Potency business from briquettes shell coconut is very big, because there is still minimal production from briquettes coconut. Whereas demand on the international market is very high. In 2019 it happened to enhance export of briquettes coconut by 4% than years before. If got attention more from government and society of course export the will the more increase. There is a number of area producer briquettes in Indonesia namely West Java (Tasikmalaya, Ciamis, Pangandaran), East Java (Banyuwangi, Lumajang, Jember), Central Java (Boyolali), Lampung and Riau. Regions the producer briquettes the largest in Indonesia (Haryati and Amir, 2021).

Based on data from book statistics coconut published by the Ministry of Estate Plantations on 5 (five) last year charcoal shell coconut exported to various countries in Asia, Europe, and the Middle East. One of the destination countries exporting main briquettes charcoal shell coconut from Indonesia is Saudi Arabia. Supported by 2018 data, it is known that Indonesia's total exports to Saudi Arabia reached a value of US\$36,554,000 and Saudi Arabia 's total imports for product briquettes worldwide reached US\$ 64,993,000 (Vanita, 2019). That shows that Indonesia only controls 56% of Saudi Arabia's export market and only utilizes half from the ability production of briquettes coconut. If reviewed more in again potency Indonesia's exports are very wide (Ministry of Commerce Republic of Indonesia. 2015). Known export volume briquettes of charcoal shell coconut to Saudi Arabia reached 18,456,759 kg with score export for \$US 18,966,251 (Laucereno. 2021). This is the biggest export volume event that happened in 2019 (Nurbidawati, 2019).

In other countries the volume of exports of briquettes and charcoal shell coconches joined follows an increase, where Request briquettes charcoal shell coconuts in various countries spelled out big Nursini and Allwar, 2019). Every year enhancement requests occur to export briquettes charcoal shell coconut, however production from briquettes is still limited in Indonesia. Whereas plantation Coconut in Indonesia covers an area of 3,728,600 hectares, with production coconut is known as 15.4 billion seed or equivalent with 3.2 million tons of copra. This shows that production of coconut in Indonesia is still relatively low with production of one ton/ha compared with 2 (two) ton/ha in the Philippines (Directorate General of Estate Plantation Republic Indonesia, 2021).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Approach economy political International based on the thought that every individual has good nature and rational, therefore that man will want a cooperation for reaching interest together called with perspective Liberalism. Perspective this challenge one liberal assumptions and foundations viz belief that connection international in conflict characteristic cooperative (Gartina and Sukriya, 2012).

Perspective liberalism focuses on positive and optimistic thinking already. It is in yourself that humans always want to build cooperation and use rationality in face of every problem. So from now there is loss earned if there are problems related internationally with conditions where two countries find awkwardness in the solution, because perspective liberal prioritize interdependence and work the same (Jackson, and Georg Sorensen. 2005).

Perspective liberals also believe that man has many needs and interests, where will need to help others through cooperative and collaborative society. Well in scale national or international as well as have a big impact towards others. because of that liberals believe that every sense thought from individuals that they could arrive at work equally profitable and the war that happened could end.

On research this analysis level is used of the Nation-State, where the state can be interpreted as an instrument for those who have power to arrange relationships individually in society and order all manifestation power in society. Reason why level nation- state analysis used because connection international basically governed by behavior a nation- state how can the state realize all ambition nation through policies as well as every citizens can help as implementation.

In study this writer use concept of international cooperation that is cooperation relationship between two countries or more for reach something destination certain. As stated by Krugman (2000), if a country trades goods and services produced with other countries, it is almost certain that the two countries that carry out the trade will benefit. Moment this there are a number of available methods for measure interdependence one country to another. International cooperation have destination for Fulfill needs nation, prevent or avoid conflict, acknowledged as independent nation, and more strengthen connection between nation. Work same this is a network based on kindness without existing violence or coercion then validated in a manner law. Underlying factors form the same work: difference, ideology, different climate, different fertility ground, different resource nature and so on.

Study this use theory interdependence where every country has dependency on each other or can say the countries each other need. Experts use comparison activity between a bilateral trade country with the total import-export of the country (Polachek, 1980). Furthermore, experts say that a country's bilateral trade will create profits, namely each country will get the opportunity to export various types of goods produced, which are produced using most of the abundant resources in the country, as well as import various goods produced using natural resources. limited resources in the country (Krugman, 2000).

III. RESEARCH METHODS

Method study this use approach qualitative descriptive. Method study is method scientific for getting data for destination certain. Method scientific could be interpreted as something activity rational, empirical, and systematic research (Darmadi, 2014).

Study qualitative is something research used to describe and analyze phenomenon, event, activity, social, belief, attitude, perception of good people individually or group (Syahrudin, et al. 2020). In study this used a secondary data type. Secondary data is the data obtained by researchers from existing sources, that is researchers do not directly take the data to the field but through intermediary media like books, journals, websites and so on (Ardianto, 2004). Secondary data in study this used for digging information more, again related with opportunity to export briquettes charcoal shell Indonesian coconut in the international market. Required information related with opportunity export briquettes charcoal shell Indonesian coconut on the international market, information to any country Indonesia does export related with briquettes charcoal shell coconut, information Indonesia's total export volume each yearly, country information that did export kind with Indonesia that is briquettes charcoal shell coconut. This data source obtained from books, journals, websites.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Development Production Export of Coconut Shell Charcoal Briquettes In Indonesia

Indonesia has very position strategic, can seen based on position astronomers in the area tropical (equatorial) so that have condition supportive climate. This is something luck for life resident. kindly Indonesia's geography is flanked by two continent namely Asia and Australia and two Oceans namely the Indian Ocean and the Pacific Ocean (Charles, 1975), which make this country be on the axis world maritime. So that influence track trade and transportation international. The stretched territory of Indonesia from Sabang to Merauke, which every island have sea big main. As a country with characteristics land and water. Indonesia borders land and sea with other countries in the world. Located on the shaft world maritime make Indonesia has long done trading with other countries through transportation the sea initiated by the King-dom's archipelago. Indonesia is located in Southeast Asia which has large land 1,913,578.68 km², water of 6/653,341,439 km², and the line beach along 99,093 km. Indonesia occupies position to seven as the largest country in the world after Russia, Canada, United States of America, China, Brazil and Australia. Indonesia occupies position second as the largest country in Southeast Asia, based on the amount of islands according to data from Department Domestic Affairs of the Republic Indonesia in 2004 are as many as 17,504 islands. Based on location Geographically, Indonesia is located between continents of Asia and Australia, as well as between the Indian and Pacific Oceans. Superiority strategic location is Indonesia which is between two the continents of Asia and Australia which are center then cross commercial for neighboring countries such as Malaysia and Singapore. Different country geographical so have different regional conditions, such as climate, source power, social culture, even system government is also different. In Thing this is Indonesia which has climate the tropics have profit that is easy for produce source power natural like results agriculture and plantations. This is what makes many other countries want to work the same with Indonesia in trading like export and import. The tropical Indonesian native is coconut. Coconut is one result of lots of plantations in demand in other countries because every part from coconut could be utilized. As a country with a tropical climate, Indonesia produces coconut. Indonesia has large land plantations of 3,654,478 hectares with total production around 3,051,585 tons and about 99% planted by small farmers (Directorate General of Estate Plantations, 2021).

Besides used for consumption domestic, commodity coconut is also exported which can be produce foreign exchange for commodity it and can made as source income economy national.

Fig. 1. Distribution Map Production Coconut in Indonesia

Source: Processed from BPS data (Central Bureau of Statistics)

Coconut is a product that functions well in the cultural, social, and economic life of Indonesian people. Utility from coconut alone not only gives the fruit just will but every part from plant coconut has many benefits (Syaharuddin, 2020). Coconut is made as a product commercial because all parts of coconut could be used to fulfill various needs. Based on analysis results, the harvest saw high investment and can give profit in a period of six years, without considering non-fruit benefits. For that, cultivation of coconut becomes a great alternative profitable, it can be taken away from a piece of coconut shell to raw material of active charcoal (Suhartana, 2016).

Table 1. Export Value Product Processed Indonesian Coconut in 2019

No	Product Name	Value (US\$)
1	Charcoal Coconut	268.99
2	Oil Coconut and its derivatives	255.13
3	Oil Coconut Raw (CCO)	188.14
4	Flour Coconut / Coconut Scar Dry	107.25
5	Fresh Coconut and its processed	75.75
6	Oil Extraction and Copra	36.46
7	Processed Coconut	39.34
8	Copra	29.53
9	Fiber Coconut	12.29

Source: Directorate General Development National Export Year 2019

Briquettes charcoal shell coconut from area Central Java dominates the Middle East market no more than 300 containers per month, every container contains 26-30 tons with turnover 2500-3000 million in every export. CV Charisma Mandiri di Kunduran, Blora every year produces briquettes of charcoal shell coconut as much as 1,700tons with production reaching IDR 12.2 billion. CV Pringgodani in Jiken, Blora produces 1,152ton charcoal shell coconuts per year, with production of IDR 11,520 billion (Laucereno,.2021). Availability and quality briquettes, charcoal shell coconuts, are actually far higher in Indonesia so that interest of foreign countries in need. Charcoal categorized as quality tall or not seen from content carbon remains what it contains. The more a lot of fixed carbon contains charcoal so the more good quality charcoal that, thing this because of this fixed carbon is source hot at the moment burning.

Export Market Share Export of Coconut Shell Charcoal Briquettes

Indonesian entrepreneurs export charcoal shell coconut to the top five world markets, including; Middle East, America, Europe, Russia, and Australia. Export briquettes charcoal shell Indonesian coconut and its derivatives experience enhancement by 4 % annually worldwide because of high demand in foreign markets for product briquettes charcoal shell coconut and lack of interest from buyers domestically. Association businessman briquettes charcoal shell coconuts say Indonesia produces between 800,000 to 1 (one) million tons of briquettes charcoal shell coconuts per year. However, the use of briquettes charcoal shell coconut for industry new reach half of the total industry briquettes charcoal shell Indonesian

coconut. Land area plantation coconuts throughout Indonesia reached 3.7 million hectare so many potency business industry briquettes charcoal shell coconut, Indonesia when this only had 350 manufacturers briquettes charcoal shell company dominated coconut small and medium-sized enterprises (Hayati and Amir, 2021).

Saudi Arabia is one of the priority countries exporting charcoal shell coconut from Indonesia. This is supported by data that import product briquettes charcoal shell coconut and its derivatives keep moving up every year. Total exports of charcoal shell coconut in 2018 from Indonesia to Saudi Arabia translucent for US\$36,554,000. Meanwhile, the country's total imports for the same product worldwide reached US\$64,993,000. The data show that Indonesia only dominates 56% of the briquette market charcoal shell Saudi Arabian coconut and only use half from capacity production briquettes charcoal shell coconut (Gartina and Surkiya, 2022). Based on BPS data it is known that the amount of briquettes charcoal shell coconut from Indonesia was as much as 188.05 thousand tons, the value of export reached USD 145.09 million. Mostly charcoal shell coconut from Indonesia exported to other countries such as China, Brazil, Germany, Lebanon, Sri Lanka, Vietnam, the Netherlands, Malaysia, Russia, and Saudi Arabia (Directorate of General of Estate Plantations, 2021). Based on the data obtained from Trend Economy, the biggest exporter group commodity in the world in 2020 is China by 18.5% of world exports (US\$464 million), followed by the United States at 14.2% (US\$356 million). India 8.9% (US\$222 million), Germany 6.35% (US\$159 million), and Belgium 5.77% (US\$144 million).

Briquette price charcoal shell coconut this show increases in all countries except the Philippines. briquette price charcoal shell coconuts in Indonesia amounted to US\$483/MT in January 2018 and reached US\$555/MT in July 2018. Meanwhile, in January 2018 prices for briquettes charcoal shell coconut in Sri Lanka reached US\$491/TM and increased to US\$525/TM in July 2018. Nope wanted to lose to India in the month of January 2018 prices the product was US\$572/TM and experienced enhancement to US\$616/MT in July 2018. Based on trend increase this could increase the Request briquettes charcoal shell coconut. Along with increase price briquettes charcoal shell coconut producer carbon active adapt price follow increase price briquettes charcoal shell coconut particularly in Sri Lanka. Carbon price active in Sri Lanka for January 2018 was US\$143/MT and on a regular basis gradually increased to US\$2,650/MT in June 2018. In early 2021, 1 (one) container of coconut charcoal briquettes was successfully exported to Turkey for the purpose of Turkey. The potential export value of coconut charcoal briquettes reaches USD 35 million per year (Consulate General Republic Indonesia Istanbul Turkey, 2021).

Fig. 2. Briquette Export of Coconut Shell Charcoal Briquettes in US\$/MT (FOB) In the Philippines, Sri Lanka, Indonesia and India January 2014-June 2018

Lack of supply briquettes charcoal shell coconut in the middle increasing market demand will make briquettes charcoal shell coconut push price briquettes charcoal shell coconut permanently strong. Briquette price charcoal shell coconut in Indonesia also experienced an increase since quarter last 2019 with price reaching US\$464/MT in the month December 2019 and on experience enhancement up to US\$596/MT in the month March 2021. Supply briquettes charcoal shell coconut in Indonesia it seems keep going continue because production more coconut low that is exacerbated by rising export coconut scar. The Philippines, India and Sri Lanka also felt an increased price from briquettes charcoal shell coconut. Product price

briquettes of charcoal shell coconuts in the Philippines reached US\$315/MT in the month December 2019 and US\$386/MT in the month March 2021. Meanwhile, Sri Lanka also experienced an increased price from US\$386/MT in December 2019 to US\$557/MT in the month March 2021. Increase price product briquettes charcoal shell Coconut is also found in India, the price of briquettes charcoal shell coconuts US\$372/MT per month on December 2019 experienced increase to to US\$621/MT per month on March 2021 (International Coconut Community, 2022).

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Briquettes charcoal shell coconut is results plantations that have experienced enhancement export, from a number of literature export briquettes charcoal shell coconut Keep going experience enhancement even in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic because exported to Egypt, Europe, Turkey, Saudi Arabia, and several other countries.

V. CONCLUSION

Coconut shell charcoal briquettes are one of the commodities that have the potential to be marketed in the international market. This is indicated by the large demand for coconut shell charcoal briquettes which is increasing every year, and the fulfillment of the demand quota is still very low, namely one third of the total demand. The high volume of export demand for coconut shells is a benchmark that the increase in export volume is important for the development of exports of coconut shell charcoal briquettes from Indonesia to various countries in the world. Among Indonesia's coconut shell export destinations are China, Brazil, Germany, Lebanon, Sri Lanka, Vietnam, Netherlands, Malaysia, Russia, and Saudi Arabia.

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